

PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS IN ORGANIC CHEMISTRY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: In this article, the development of higher education by solving the pedagogical problem, its perspectives and the professional preparation of the student, together with the analysis of the teaching of chemistry as its direction, the identification of priorities in our research, the main directions of its implementation and It is explained about the possibility of defining approaches.

Key words: technological development, chemistry, vocational training, pedagogical problem, integrative approach

of technological development of society , development, control, etc. students from chemistry have become indicators of professional training . This was also reflected in the education system, which went on the path of rationalization and management. Therefore, in the science of pedagogy and educational practice, the question of finding qualitatively different ways of organizing and managing the educational process as a basis for increasing its quality and efficiency has arisen. One of these methods, thanks to the research of VP Bespalko, VV Guzeeva, ESZair-Beck, NEKuznesova and others, recognized the idea of technologyization of education, which led to the emergence of a new branch of science - pedagogical technology [50,133, 168, etc.].

Development of higher education by solving the pedagogical problem , its analysis of perspectives and professional training of the student with chemistry teaching as his field allowed us to determine the priority directions in our

research, to define the main directions and approaches of its implementation. All of them are important elements of his methodology.

At the same time, the justification of the research methodology cannot be completely objective without determining the level of implementation of pedagogical innovations in real educational practice. Therefore, we studied the practice of teaching chemistry at school and the state of professional training of the chemistry teacher. This made it possible to identify their existing contradictions and define ways to eliminate them.

Determination of the level of implementation of the integrated approach in educational practice as one of the pedagogical innovations was carried out by us in the process of determining the research in conducting a pedagogical experiment. At the same time, we tried to analyze and evaluate the practice of professional training of students in higher education institutions together with the practice of organic chemistry and additional pedagogical education , because we came from the understanding of their close integrative relationship.

First of all, we turned to the study of the practice of teaching chemistry, because it was important to see the environment for the work we have to prepare young teachers and to update it consistently. At the same time, we paid special attention to the implementation of the ideas and principles of developmental education, recognized as a priority in science, and the level of modernization of education.

We used various diagnostic methods to obtain reliable data. Attend chemistry classes in schools and analyze them . As a result, we came to the conclusion that the practice of teaching chemistry is mainly focused on the reproductive activity of schoolchildren. Thus, the observation of lessons revealed the dominant role of the teacher in teaching . The teacher not only presented the educational material in a ready general form, but also fully explained the process of solving the problem by the student on the blackboard.

It should be noted that even when more problematic questions are raised,

teachers do not give opportunities and time to students to answer them themselves. They appeal to the desire to save study time and present as much learning material as possible in the lesson. School textbooks do not contribute to the problematic study of chemistry, in which chemistry appears as a static system of knowledge, devoid of contradictions and scientific disputes, which must be memorized and reproduced. Most of the questions and tasks in the lesson have a reproductive nature and their solution is based on algorithms known to schoolchildren. However, in recent years there have been positive changes in this regard.

the integrative approach , it should be noted that interdisciplinary integrations in chemistry education are much better implemented. More teachers use them. They are also reflected in the content of school textbooks. At the same time, as a result of the analysis of the students' answers, it was found that the low level of systematic knowledge and its information-reproductive character, as well as the insufficient level of formation of the skills of interdisciplinary integration in independent research activities of schoolchildren.

We developed questionnaires for teachers and students in order to obtain more detailed information about the problem of the state of practice of teaching chemistry , which allows us to determine their attitude towards integrative education and the idea of building it on an integrative basis. In addition, we tried to determine the level of perceptions of schoolchildren about scientific methods of knowledge and to determine the pedagogical problem of their attitude to the studied natural sciences, including chemistry:

The vast majority of chemistry teachers are well aware of the importance of integrative education in forming students' cognitive interest, developing their mental abilities and logical thinking. However, a high percentage of teachers do not use integrative education in their practice at all or use it occasionally;

teachers do not apply to the integrative approach or do not use it from time to time are low control over the mental activity of students, a lot of time is spent

on setting and solving educational problems;

when using the integrative approach, teachers face difficulties such as lack of methodical literature, low level of development of logical thinking, general preparation. Difficulties in the implementation of interdisciplinary integration are associated with the lack of literature, the complexity of their analysis and selection for the lesson, general preparation .

most teachers use interdisciplinary integrations in time, that is, connections according to a chronological criterion. But only a few use their organizational and methodical types.

many teachers tried to build the problem on the basis of integration and considered such construction of the educational process appropriate and important for the school.

be given to the conclusion reflecting the reasons why teachers do not want to use an integrative approach . The evidence provided by them indicates that their professional and methodical knowledge in the field of integrative education theory and methodology, especially related to the issues of activation and rationalization of problem-research activities, is insufficient. Consequently, these issues are not given enough attention in the practice of training universities and improving the qualifications of professors and teachers.

Based on the obtained information on the studied pedagogical problem, the following conclusions were reached:

most of the students are not satisfied with the current practice of teaching chemistry and want to prove themselves in independent learning knowledge, in class and solving problems . At the same time, schoolchildren emphasized that education is focused on memorizing and reproducing the material presented by the teacher;

he is interested in methods of solving educational problems such as experiment, research, discussion, integration of knowledge from other subjects . In addition, he considers knowledge integration to be an interesting way to solve

problems and considers it important and effective.

Most of the students find it difficult to define methodological concepts such as the essence of scientific knowledge . 'problem', 'experiment', 'hypothesis', 'law', 'theory' cannot establish a connection between them and is not familiar with or has a wrong idea about the methods. At the same time, 62.6% of respondents consider this knowledge important and necessary for them.

Most of the students do not want to study chemistry despite their positive attitude. However, the majority of schoolchildren for one reason or another are interested in natural sciences in general. The main reasons for difficulty in understanding chemistry: the complexity of the theoretical material and its misunderstanding, as well as the insignificance of chemical experiments in classes. At the same time, the chemical experiment took the leading place among the factors that attract students to study this subject.

At the same time, in the course of the research, we found that schoolchildren's level of mastery of logical thinking methods and elements of creative thinking such as encoding and decoding information in symbolic-graphic expressions is low.

For example, when we offer students assignments on comparing, classifying, interpreting tables, graphs, we find that most of them we encountered that they do not understand the essence of the methods of mental activity.

Thus, the results of the task of comparing the chemical properties of soluble and insoluble bases showed that the majority of students could not understand the comparison as a simple description of objects. This technique does not have a structure and an algorithm for its implementation. In addition, schoolchildren demonstrated a low level of experimental skills and research methods.

Thus, the information obtained by us made it possible to identify pedagogical problems in teaching chemistry at school and determine ways to eliminate them. At the same time, we assumed that most of them are related to pedagogical problems in professional training . This prompted us to start

analyzing its situation in higher and further education.

the study of psychological and pedagogical sciences among students during the period of professional training showed that their psychological, pedagogical and professional training is insufficient, and in some cases extremely low. Also, he did not know anything about developmental education and integrative education among his students who started studying chemistry teaching methods course. He had a superficial idea about them from previous courses in psychology and pedagogy .

He had a superficial understanding of the teaching tools, methods and forms used in the modern school. Similar levels of student knowledge were found in such leading pedagogies, especially in the context of an integrative approach, such as intra- and interdisciplinary integrations. These data made it possible to assess the quality of students' initial training and, on this basis, to create a system of their professional training and determine its quality management strategy.

According to the results of the study of problems conducted among students who studied in a similar specialty in higher education , students were introduced to these types of studies in classes on pedagogy, psychology and other subjects. - However, they all stated that they had no knowledge of integrative. In the lesson, the issues of building education on an integrative basis were not mentioned at all, it is worth noting the information obtained during the survey of students who also studied some methodical sciences.

Thus, higher education institutions 80% of the 3rd year students of the faculty of natural sciences, who studied the basics of chemistry teaching methods and technologies, noted that they were not familiar with the theory and methods of problem-based teaching of chemistry. The same number of respondents stated that they do not have an integrated approach to learning. At the same time, the students unanimously accepted that the issues of construction of problematic materials were not considered in the lessons on chemistry teaching methods and technologies.

noted that most of the 3rd-year students get acquainted with developmental and problem-based teaching in lectures on the methodology of teaching chemistry . At the same time, they all agree that their level of knowledge is expressed by mastering the definition of each of these types of education. However, the students of the groups in which the issues of the integrative educational methodology were considered in the practical training, nevertheless, noted that its consideration was carried out in a general plan, without forming appropriate algorithms for the teacher's actions. In general, he believes that students have not mastered the methodology of problem-based teaching of chemistry, noted that they are not familiar with the issues of building it on an integrative basis in the classroom.

In general, comparing the results of the problems studied by the students , it can be noted that the developing and integrative educational issues in higher education institutions are given more attention by teachers. However, the level of students' mastery of the basics of their implementation at school is still not sufficient to solve the current tasks of modernizing general chemistry education, including reorienting it to educational ideas and principles that develop on the basis of an integrative approach.

We explain this by the fact that the ideas of integrative education are implemented in the preparation of students, mainly at the level of content. At the same time, they do not serve as a basis for organizing and managing the cognitive activity of students in learning and mastering it. This significantly reduces the level of perception, understanding and value-motivational understanding of the features of the educational systems that we are considering, and thus prevents their use in cognitive and professional activities.

Our conclusion is confirmed by the results of studying the motivations of students' cognitive activity, their preference for certain ways of organizing it, and their perception of the compatibility of the methods of teaching subjects taught in higher education institutions with these motives and methods of activity.

At the same time, the analysis of the literature shows that the issues of updating the professional training of chemistry students in science and practice have been raised and resolved. Thus, he proposed and tested a way to improve the practical orientation of the laboratory seminar on chemistry teaching methodology by forming a system of skills for planning and preparing chemistry lessons in students. At the same time, he established two options for building laboratory and seminar training, conditionally called "chemical" and "didactic" [464, 465, etc.].

The essence of the "chemical" option is to form the named skills of students by learning the methods of teaching certain educational subjects. In this case, the sequence of topics in the school chemistry course unites the classes. While solving the pedagogical problem in the teaching process, it is based on the model of step-by-step performance of actions by the teacher in preparing and conducting a chemistry lesson. The following activities are leading among them: 1) analysis of educational goals and the content of the subject and its lessons; 2) choosing the logic of reviewing the content of the lesson and organizing the cognitive activity of schoolchildren in it; 3) search for ways to give the lesson a problematic character by determining the system of its cognitive tasks; 4) selection of didactic and methodological support of the lesson, including its quality control; 5) making a lesson outline [465 and others].

the importance of the "lesson approach" in the fact that only through chemistry lessons, students can acquire the skills and experience of professional-methodical activity in the conditions of the integrative approach that we use. Thus, understanding the role of the experiment, mastering the techniques and methods of its preparation and conducting will be more effective if it is considered in the classroom in a specific lesson structure. In this, the student sees his place in the forms, methods and system of experience .

Understands the connection between the educational tools used in the lesson, their tasks and the content of the program, can effectively use the experience in explaining new things for material and other purposes . In addition,

the efficiency of discussion and mastering of these issues will be higher if they are considered in the lesson through the formation of teaching-methodical problems.

We believe that it is also important to ensure the continuity of the professional training of chemistry teachers. In this regard, we consider it promising to prepare it in the educational process, because it is possible to ensure the integration of educational systems related to the professional training of the student.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S., & Boxodirjon o'g'li, V. A. (2022). XORIJ PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 39-47.
2. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 176-182.
3. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.
4. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
5. Ботирова, Н. (2020). Обучающие возможности тестовых технологий. *Профессиональное образование и общество*, (3), 68-71.
6. Ботирова, Н. Д. (2019). Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (61), 4-6.
7. Ботирова, Н. Д. Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников development of productive thinking of younger schoolboys. *Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным*

наукам. Подробнее на, 4.

8. Ботирова, Н. Д., & Алимджонова, М. Ю. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИ ЭВРИСТИК ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ТАШКИЛИЙ ОМИЛЛАРИ. Scientific progress, 3(4), 519-524.

9. Botirova Nasiba Djurabayevna INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS . Eastern European Scientific Journal Germany. 128 – 132 p. <http://www.auris-verlag.de>

10. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 914-917.

11. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 1040-1044.

12. Alimjanova, M. (2021). ABOUT GENDER STEREOTYPES. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), 2(06), 72-76.

13. Janabergenova, A. J. (2018). Organization and Forms of Students' Independent Work on Higher Mathematics at Pedagogical University. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (2).

14. Janabergenova, A. J. (2021). Setting Goals on Smart Techniques and Affecting Student Motivation. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 9333-9336.

15. Askarova, D. (2022). FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND BOOKREADERS QUALITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1039-1044.

16. Askarova, D. I. (2022). The Role Of Folk Pedagogy In The Development Of Creativity Of Students Of Higher Educational Institutions. Oriental Journal of Social Sciences, 2(02), 89-96.

17. Dilafruz, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarda Va Oilada Gender

Xususiyatlarni Shakllantirish Omillari. Innovation In The Modern Education System, 2(18), 183-189.

18. Askarova, D. I. (2022). USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), 3(10), 92-97.

19. Askarova, D. I., & Jabborova, M. K. (2022). The Introduction Of Gender Issues In Preschool Education On The Example Of Folk Pedagogy. Oriental Journal of Social Sciences, 2(05), 81-87.

20. Jabborova, M. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 129-132.

21. Jabborova, M. (2022). BO'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNI TAYYORLASH TIZIMIDA MALAKAVIY AMALIYOTNING ROLI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 167-173.

22. Kodiraliyevna, J. M. (2022). TARBIYACHI KASBINING MA'NAVIY AXLOQIY NEGIZLARI. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 2), 64-70.

23. Zhabborova, M. R. K. (2021). Мактабгача таълим соҳаси талабаларида бошқарувчанлик қобилиятларини ривожлантириш. *Молодой ученый*, (17), 394-395.

24. Dilafruz, Y., Marifatxon, J., Rasuljonovna, E. Z., & Muqaddasxon, M. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМГА YANGICHA YONDASHUV. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 3), 121-125.

25. E. Najmiddinov, A. Rasujonov, & J. Rahimov (2022). FARG'ONA VODIYSI SUV HAVZALARIDAGI BALIQLAR GELMINTLARI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 145-151. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335759

26. Najmiddinov, Eldor , Rasuljonov, Adhamjon, & Rahimov, Javohir (2022).

FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10), 1049-1054.

27. E. Najmiddinov (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА “ИХТИОЛОГИЯ ВА ГИДРОБИОЛОГИЯ” СОҲАЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 152-160. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335800

28. E. Najmiddinov (2022). TABIATNING MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI BARKAMOL AVLOD BO'LIB SHAKLLANISHIDAGI ANAMIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B8), 149-154. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7336353

29. Юлдашев, Э., & Нажмиддинов, Э. (2013). БРАКОНИДЫ (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) РОДА ROGAS NEES ФАУНЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ. In *Биоразнообразие и рациональное использование природных ресурсов* (pp. 134-136).

30. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., Кучбоев, А. Э., Мухаммадиев, М. А., & Соатов, Б. Б. (2021). Эколого-морфологические характеристики нематод рода *Rhabdochona*-паразитов обыкновенной маринки. *Теория и практика борьбы с паразитарными болезнями*, (22), 387-393.

31. Kuchboev, A. E., Najmidinov, E. K., Mukhamediev, M. A., Karimova, R. R., & Yildiz, K. (2021). Morphological and ecological features of some nematodes of the genus *Rhabdochona* in marinka obtained from Fergana Valley, Uzbekistan. *Journal of Parasitic Diseases*, 45(4), 1084-1089.

32. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 326-329.

33. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). METHODOLOGICAL SUPPORT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 74-76.
34. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 97-102.
35. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 235-239.
36. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 121-123.
37. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289-292.
38. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.

39. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 235-239.
40. Asqarov Anvarjon Rahimjon o‘g‘li. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING AQLIY TARAQQIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHIDA O‘YIN RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI FAOLIYAT SIFATIDA. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 207–209.
41. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.
42. To‘lqinovna, Y. D. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA МАТЕМАТИК ТАСАВВУРЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ МЕТОДЛАРИ. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 25-31.
43. Yuldasheva Dilshoda To‘Lqinovna (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA BADIY TASVIRLAR ORQALI IZCHIL NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521
44. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE

ACQUISITION. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 124-130.

45. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 10, 32-35.
46. Ummatqulov, T. (2022). INSON SOG'LOM BO'LISHIDA VALEOLOGIYA FANINING AHAMIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 80-88.
47. SultonaliMannopov, A., AbdusalomSoliev, U., & TokhirShokirov, R. (2021). Development of Uzbek National Singing Art during Independence. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 6845-6853.
48. Шокиров, Т. Н. (2022). МИЛЛИЙ МУСИҚА МАДАНИЯТИ ВА УНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ (фольклор, дostonчилик, мақом мисолида). *Science and innovation*, 1(С3), 31-38.
49. Shakirov, T. N. (2022). SUCCESSION IS THE MAIN PRINCIPLE OF DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL MUSIC CULTURE. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(06), 1-10.
50. Шокиров, Т. Н. (2022). АБУ НАСР ФОРОБИЙНИНГ МУСИҚА ИЛМИГА ҚЎШГАН ҲИССАСИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 353-359.
51. Nurmamatovich, S. T. (2021). Theoretical of national music culture fundamentals.
52. Qizi, G. S., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). The use of anthroponyms and pseudonyms in alisher Navoi's gazelles. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 349-353.

53. Tillaboyeva, G., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). ALISHER NAVOIY ASARLARIDA BADIY TAXALLUSLARNING QO‘LLANILISHI. *Студенческий вестник*, (13-5), 70-72.
54. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). ALISHER NAVOIY SHE’RIYATIDA “SHAXS” TUSHUNCHASI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 182-196.
55. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA LIBOS NOMLARI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 506-514.
56. Mohinur, D., & Rahimjon, U. (2022). A Study Of Memory Processes And Their Development In Preschool. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 62-65.
57. Rahim, U. (2021, May). SOCIAL FACTORS OF THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF MENTAL AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 6-7).
58. Usmonov, R. (2022). O‘SMIRLAR XULQIDA NAMOIYISHKORLIK G‘AYRATLILIK XUSUSIYATLARI TADQIQ ETISH METODOLOGIYASI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 127-135.
59. Usmonov, R. (2022). O‘SMIRLIK DAVRI SHAXSIGA XOS ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDOSHUVLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 120-126.
60. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOIYISHKORLIK, G‘AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO‘LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
61. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOIYISHKORLIK, G‘AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON

BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.

62. Rakhmonovich, U. R. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 820-824.
63. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.
64. Қурбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
65. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).
66. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). О 'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.
67. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). CHET EL OLIMLARI TOMONIDAN GURUHDAGI O 'SMIRLAR VA AUTSAYDERLAR MUAMMOSINI O 'RGANILISHNING OZIGA XOSLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 33-38.
68. Noxida, D., & Saida, Q. (2022). TALABA QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA

TAYYORLASHNING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 309-314.

69. Dilshodbek O'g'li, R. S. (2022). The Role Of Physical Culture In Providing The Psychological Health Of The Athlete. *Innovative Developments And Research In Education, Canada*.

70. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH–IJTIMOIY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 66-70.

71. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 215-221.

72. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 256-259.